

On recognition of "primary data" producers through DOI of "secondary" data

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Adding permanent identifiers (DOIs) to datasets is an important practice for data citation providing attribution to researchers and contributors who create, process, manage data (hereinafter "data producers"). This data-DOI practice is becoming increasingly popular and is gradually being extended to many more scientific communities. In specific scientific disciplines (e.g., Earth and Planetary Sciences), some studies are conducted based on data directly retrieved from experiments, observations, and/or simulation, etc. (hereinafter "primary" data or PD), while there are other studies based on data generated from compilation and/or further data processing of PD (hereinafter "secondary" data or SD). SD is sometimes generated from processing multiple PD products (e.g., at different geographical locations, at different time, at different observational techniques/conditions and so on). In a research field where SD is more popularly used, the current data-DOI mechanism may not be sufficient in supporting data producers to keep sustainability of their data creation/curation/management works of PDs, because it is often difficult to ensure they receive proper recognition (and with it, enhanced reputation) even when SD generated from their PD products are used frequently and correctly cited in a number of research papers. In this paper, we attempt to focus on this difficulty for PD producers and we propose a revision in a metadata schema that enables the PD producers' work is appropriately recognized.